

Spectroscopic Investigation of some Thio Schiff Bases

Y. M. ISSA^{*}, M. M. OMAR, H. M. ABDEL-FATTAH and A. A. SOLIMAN

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt

Manuscript received 21 May 1993, revised 18 April 1994, accepted 27 May 1994

Schiff bases of 2-aminothiophenol with some benzaldehyde derivatives have been prepared. The effect of substitution at the benzal ring on the band positions of $\nu_{C=N}$ and $\delta_{CH(CH=N)}$ is investigated; the electron-withdrawing groups lower the frequency as a result of decreased electron density on the C=N linkage while electron-donating groups exert an opposite effect. Band assignment of the proper absorption band is made and correlated with the non-coplanar structure assumed to the Schiff base molecules; the effect of substituents is also studied. The chemical shifts of the different types of protons in the nmr spectra of the prepared Schiff bases are also reported.

Schiff bases are the subject of many spectral studies. A clear understanding of the electronic structure and spectral properties for the explanation of their photochemical properties, phototropism and photoisomerism was the aim of these studies¹⁻⁶. Several investigations concluded the noncoplanarity of the Schiff base molecule based on uv, ir and nmr spectroscopic studies^{3,4,7}.

The present communication deals with the spectroscopic investigation of some new Schiff bases (1a-h) derived from 2-aminothiophenol. The results of spectral studies are discussed in relation to molecular structure and substituent effect.

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|---|-----------------------------------|
| a: X = H | e: X = <i>p</i> -NO ₂ |
| b: X = <i>p</i> -Cl | f: X = <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ |
| c: X = <i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ | g: X = <i>p</i> -CH ₃ |
| d: X = <i>p</i> -OH | h: X = <i>o</i> -OH |

Results and Discussion

Infrared spectra : The infrared absorption spectra of Schiff bases have been the subject of several investigations⁷⁻¹⁰. Many of these studies^{7,10} were concerned with hydroxy Schiff bases. The infrared spec-

tral data of the Schiff bases are listed in Table 1.

There are three common characteristic vibrations for the investigated Schiff bases; ν_{SH} , $\nu_{C=N}$ and $\gamma_{CH(CH=N)}$.

The SH vibration in thiophenols^{11,12} is well defined but rather weak absorption at 3 000–2 500 cm⁻¹. The SH link is not capable of the extensive degree of hydrogen bonding which occurs with OH and NH groupings. There are very little change in frequency of SH absorptions on passing from the liquid state to dilute solutions, so that any intermolecular bonding effects must be very small. For the Schiff bases under investigation (1a-h) the SH vibration appears as a weak band in the range 2 920–2 810 cm⁻¹.

A good deal of work has been done on the position of the C=N stretching absorption in various classes of compounds⁸. The band remains a difficult one to identify, however, owing to the considerable changes in intensity which follow changes in its environment. Also, the information available on the effects of conjugation in ring systems are often conflicting and indecisive. This is partly due to the fact that in many of the compounds studied the conjugation is with C=C links and the frequencies of the two are so close that, in ring systems at least, it is doubtful whether either can be regarded as retaining its individual character. In general, the C=N stretching band in open-chain saturated compounds and in the unconjugated cyclic

TABLE I-BAND ASSIGNMENT OF IR SPECTRAL DATA (cm^{-1}) OF SCHIFF BASES **1a-h**

1a	1b	1c	1d	1e	1f	1g	1h	Assignment
-	-	-	3 180w	-	-	-	3 280b	ν_{OH}
3 080m	3 060m	3 060m	3 060w	3 078w	3 000m	3 080w	3 080m	Arom. ν_{CH}
2 990w	3 000w	2 995w	3 000w	2 944	2 980w	2 900	2 900w	Aliph. ν_{CH}
2 920w	2 920w	2 810w	2 910w	2 849w	2 820m	2 810w	2 810w	ν_{SH}
1 590w	1 598s	1 600s	1 605s	1 600s	1 610s	1 608m	1 615m	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$
1 580m	1 570m	1 580m	1 590m	1 523s	1 590m	1 592m	1 590s	Arom. C=C
968s	970s	975s	975s	974s	975s	972s	1 030s	$\gamma_{\text{CH(CH=N)}}$ out-of-plane

s = strong, b = broad, m = medium, w = weak.

system, appears in the region $1\ 690\text{--}1\ 640\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ with variable intensities^{13,14}. Conjugation lowers the frequency slightly ($1\ 660\text{--}1\ 630\ \text{cm}^{-1}$)¹⁵. When the nitrogen atom of the C=N attains greater polar character, the stretching frequency alters greatly and an overall range of $1\ 660\text{--}1\ 480\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ has been quoted for such systems¹⁵.

The Schiff bases under investigation display the C=N band within the range $1\ 615\text{--}1\ 590\ \text{cm}^{-1}$. These bands are strong except that of **1a** which is very weak one appearing at $1\ 590\ \text{cm}^{-1}$. The lowering in frequency for these compounds is attributed to the conjugation of the lone-pair of the azomethine nitrogen with the phenyl ring of the amine part.

The CH(CH=N) bands are intense bands observed in the $1\ 030\text{--}968\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ region and can not be sharply differentiated from those of the CH aromatic vibration.

For the Schiff bases **1d** and **1h**, the ν_{OH} bands ($3\ 180$ and $3\ 280\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ respectively) are broad and found at lower wave numbers with respect to that of the free OH group ($3\ 700\text{--}3\ 500\ \text{cm}^{-1}$). This may be attributed to the participation of the OH group of **1d** and **1h** in intermolecular and intramolecular hydrogen bonding respectively^{7,16}.

The effect of substitution at the benzal ring on the band positions of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and $\gamma_{\text{CH(CH=N)}}$ is investigated by plotting the relation between the $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ or $\gamma_{\text{CH(CH=N)}}$ band positions with the Hammett substituent constant (σ_{X}), (Fig. 1). Straight lines with negative slopes were obtained in both the cases which in-

Fig. 1. Dependence of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and $\gamma_{\text{CH(CH=N)}}$ on Hammett substituent constant.

dicates that electron-withdrawing groups lower the frequency as a result of decreased electron density on the C=N linkage while electron-donating groups exert an opposite effect. The dependence of the $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and $\gamma_{\text{CH(CH=N)}}$ vibrations on the different substitutions on the benzal ring reflects the planarity of the $-\text{CH=N}$ moiety with the benzal ring in the Schiff base molecule. The Hammett equation in the form,

$$\nu_x = \nu_{11} + \rho\sigma_x$$

may be applied. The equations for both $\nu_{C=N}$ and $\delta_{C-H(CH=N)}$ bands are

$$\nu_x (C=N) = 1602 - 8.33 \sigma_x$$

and

$$\gamma_x CH(CH=N) = 973 - 5.00 \sigma_x$$

Table 2 summarises the above relations. The slope (ρ), the intercept (c), the standard deviation (s) and the correlation coefficient (r) were computed using the least-squares method¹⁷. The correlation coefficient (r) in case of $\nu_{C=N}$ amounts to 0.63 indicating a fairly good influence of the azomethine stretching frequency by the substituent. This confirms the previously reported results that the azomethine is coplanar with the benzal ring¹⁸. However, the correlation coefficient in case of $\gamma_{C-H(CH=N)}$ has a low value, which may be explained on the basis that such band is present in the neighbourhood of the bands due to δ_{C-H} of the substituted benzenes. Thus it seems to be difficult to identify its correct position. The negative slopes (ρ) of the resulting lines indicate that such bands shift to lower wave numbers under the influence of electron-withdrawing groups. The values of the intercept (c) corresponding to the unsubstituted derivative amount

to 1602 and 973 cm^{-1} for $\nu_{C=N}$ and $\gamma_{C-H(CH=N)}$ respectively. The former value coincides well with that obtained practically while the latter deviates by 5 cm^{-1} .

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of the Schiff bases are presented in Fig. 2, from the structural and substituent effect point of view. The spectra

Fig. 2. Electronic absorption spectra of **1a-h** in ethanol ($5 \times 10^{-5} M$)

of the Schiff bases (**1a-g**) comprise mainly four bands (A, B, C and E) while the spectrum of (**1h**) exhibits five absorption bands (A, B, C, D and E). The $\lambda_{\max}$ of these bands are listed along with the corresponding molar absorptivities in Table 3. Band-A observed in the range 205–215 nm may be assigned to the medium energy $\pi-\pi^*$ transition within the benzene ring of the Schiff bases, in particular the N-phenyl ring which is supported by its high molar absorptivity amounting to $4.14 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Band-B, which is observed in the range 218–248 nm, may be assigned to the medium energy $\pi-\pi^*$ transition within the benzal ring with molar absorptivity of 2.64×10^4 (Ref. 19). The presence of two separated bands (A and B) may be considered as a proof of the non-coplanarity of the two aromatic rings of the Schiff bases²⁰. The high intensity of band-A can be explained on the basis of the conjugation of the unshared pair of electrons on the nitrogen atom with the N-phenyl ring of the aminothiophenol part of the Schiff bases. This implies a non-coplanar molecular structure, since the

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF $\nu_{C=N}$ AND $\gamma_{C-H(CH=N)}$ OF THE AZOMETHINE BANDS ON THE HAMMETT SUBSTITUENT (CONSTANT (σ_x) OF **1a-f**)

Compd. no	X	σ_x	$\nu_{C=N}$ cm^{-1}	$\gamma_{C-H(CH=N)}$ cm^{-1}
1a	H	0.00	1600	968
b	<i>p</i> -Cl	+0.23	1598	970
c	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂	-0.83	1600	975
d	<i>p</i> -OH	-0.37	1605	975
e	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	+0.78	1600	974
f	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	-0.27	1610	975
g	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	-0.17	1608	972
Slope (ρ)			-2.92	-1.87
Standard deviation (s)			4.84	2.90
Intercept (c)			1602	973
Correlation coefficient (r)			0.63	0.36

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS OF SCHIFF BASES OF **1a-h**

Compd. no.	Band A		Band B		Band C		Band D		Band E	
	$\lambda_{\max}$ nm	$\epsilon_{\max} \times 10^{-4}$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	$\lambda_{\max}$ nm	$\epsilon_{\max} \times 10^{-4}$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	$\lambda_{\max}$ nm	$\epsilon_{\max} \times 10^{-4}$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	$\lambda_{\max}$ nm	$\epsilon_{\max} \times 10^{-4}$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	$\lambda_{\max}$ nm	$\epsilon_{\max} \times 10^{-4}$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
1a	208	4.14	226	2.50	250	0.96	-	-	298	2.28
b	207	3.90	226	2.64	250	1.08	-	-	300	2.60
c	205	2.94	220	1.86	240 ^a	1.40	-	-	348	2.70
d	215	3.52	248	0.72	258	0.66	-	-	315	3.06
e	205	2.88	218	2.28	240	0.96	-	-	334	1.80
f	213	3.66	246	0.81	256	0.78	-	-	312	3.06
g	208	4.14	226 ^a	2.04	248	1.10	-	-	298	2.10
h	214	3.72	248	1.04	258	1.02	286	1.26	332	1.50

^aShoulder.

N-phenyl ring can only conjugate with the nitrogen lone-pair if the latter ring is rotated out-of-the plane of the conjugated system consisting of the benzal part and the azomethine group⁷. Band-C lying within the range 240–256 nm, may be assigned to the low energy $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the phenyl moiety. The broad band-E located at 298–348 nm can be assigned to the $\pi-\pi^*$ electronic transition within the CH=N linkage influenced by charge transfer interaction within the entire molecule. In case of the Schiff base **1h**, which has an OH group in *ortho*-position to the $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$, the additional band at 286 nm may be attributed to the $\pi-\pi^*$ within the ring formed as a result of the participation of the *o*-OH group in a hydrogen chelate ring¹⁶.

Substituent effect : The CT bands display a marked shift with the change in nature and position of the substituent on the arylidene ring. Generally, the bands due to the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the aromatic ring display small shift due to changed molecular structure. The plot of $\lambda_{\max}$ of the CT band 'E' against the Hammett substitution constant (σ_x)^{17–21} is shown in Fig. 3. The linear relationship indicates that the position of the CT band is directly affected by the nature of the substituents. The red-shift decreases as the electron-donating property of the substituent (X) decreases on going from X = *p*-N(CH₃)₂ to X = H, resulting in decrease of the opportunity of CT.

Fig. 3. Relation between $\lambda_{\max}$ of the Schiff bases and σ_x of the substituents.

On the other hand, the increase of the red-shift in case of *p*-Cl and *p*-NO₂ may be attributed to an increase of CT in the reverse direction caused by the electron-attracting properties of these substituents⁶,

¹H nmr spectra : Nmr spectroscopy has been proved useful in establishing the nature and structure of many Schiff bases in solutions^{23,24}. Nmr spectra of all the Schiff bases exhibit a singlet at δ 2.4–2.6, assigned to

the CH₃ proton of the solvent. Two multiplet signals, of integrations corresponding to 10 protons in case of **1a** and 9 protons for all the other Schiff bases (**1b-h**) observed at δ 6.5–8.4, are due to the aromatic protons. The presence of two multiplet signals may be explained on the basis that the protons of the two aromatic rings are not equally shielded. The protons of the N-phenyl ring are more shielded due to conjugation of the lone-pair of electrons of the nitrogen atom with the π -system of the phenyl ring shifting the signal upfield. The other downfield multiplet is attributed to the less shielded benzyl ring protons. The singlet appearing at δ 3.4 with an integration corresponding to one proton in all the Schiff bases, is assigned to the SH proton.

The nmr spectra of **1d** and **1h** showed sharp signals at δ 10.15 and 10.90 respectively, with an integration value corresponding to 1 proton in each case which can be assigned to the OH proton. However, the OH proton in case of **1h** is more deshielded as it is involved in an intramolecular hydrogen bond¹⁶. The signal of the aliphatic protons of the CH₃ group of **1g** appeared as a singlet at δ 3.4 along with that of the SH proton with an integration corresponding to 4 protons. Schiff base **1c** showed two signals at δ 3.4 and 3.0 ppm. The first signal with integration corresponding to 4 protons can be assigned to one of the CH₃ groups of the N(CH₃)₂ group overlapped with the SH group, and the latter signal with an integration corresponding to 3 protons is assigned to the other CH₃ group of the N,N-dimethyl group.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of pure laboratory grade (B.D.H.). The Schiff bases were prepared by condensation of equimolecular amounts of 2-aminothiophenol with the corresponding aldehyde⁷ and crystallised from ethanol: **1a**, m.p. 112°; **b**, 119°; **c**, 139°; **d**, 224°; **e**, 221°; **f**, 121°; **g**, 60°; **h**, 128°. Elemental analyses for C, H, N, S and Cl (carried out at Microanalytical Centre, Cairo University) were found satisfactory.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on Pye-Unicam SP 3-300 and Perkin-Elmer 1430 infrared spectrometers, electronic spectra (ethanol) on a Perkin-Elmer SP Lambda 3 with R 100 A recorder using 1-cm matched quartz cells and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Gemini 200 Varian spectrometer (200 MHz) and the spectra extended from 0 to 15 ppm.

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